

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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FEATURES AND PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN UZBEKISTAN

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna

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Abstract: In this article, we consider online promotion tools, including search engine optimization (SEO), contextual advertising, social networks (SMM), email marketing and content strategies, the impact of digital technologies on consumer behavior and business adaptation to new trends, the effectiveness of online promotion in the context of the digital transformation of the economy of Uzbekistan.

Key words: digital marketing, Uzbekistan, SEO, SMM, content marketing, online advertising, targeting, internet promotion, e-commerce, digital strategies.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada onlayn reklama vositalari, jumladan, qidiruv tizimini optimallashtirish (SEO), kontekstli reklama, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar marketingi (SMM), elektron pochta marketingi va kontent strategiyalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Shuningdek, raqamli texnologiyalarning iste'molchilar xatti-harakati va biznesning yangi tendensiyalarga moslashuviga ta'siri hamda O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotining raqamli transformatsiyasi sharoitida onlayn reklamanning samaradorligi tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli marketing, O'zbekiston, SEO, SMM, kontent marketingi, onlayn reklama, maqsadlilik, internetda ilgari surish, elektron tijorat, raqamli strategiyalar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются инструменты интернет-продвижения, включая поисковую оптимизацию (SEO), контекстную рекламу, социальные сети (SMM), email-маркетинг и контент-стратегии, влияние цифровых технологий на поведение потребителей и адаптацию бизнеса к новым трендам, эффективность интернет-продвижения в условиях цифровой трансформации экономики Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: цифровой маркетинг, Узбекистан, SEO, SMM, контент-маркетинг, интернет-реклама, таргетинг, интернет-продвижение, электронная коммерция, цифровые стратегии.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Uzbekistan has seen rapid development of digital technologies, which has a significant impact on the marketing strategies of companies. Digital marketing is becoming an integral part of business processes, allowing enterprises to effectively interact with the target audience and expand their presence in the market.

In order to create favorable conditions for the development of the digital economy and ensure the rights of participants in the electronic market, a number of regulatory legal acts have been adopted in Uzbekistan. Thus, on January 16, 2024, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-896 "On Amendments and Supplements to Certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted.¹This law is aimed at improving the system of legal protection of intellectual property objects, which is directly related to digital content and marketing materials.

In addition, on November 30, 2023, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-381 "On measures to strengthen the protection of the rights of consumers of digital products (services) and the fight against offenses committed through digital technologies" was issued.²According to this document, the National Agency for Promising Projects of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been appointed as the authorized body in the field of regulation and development of electronic commerce, which emphasizes the importance of state control and support in this area.

In December 2024, the Cabinet of Ministers adopted Resolution No. 885, which enshrines new approaches to the development of e-commerce in the country.³The document covers the improvement of the regulatory

1 <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/6756677>

2 <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/7284840>

3 <https://nuz.uz/2024/12/30/v-uzbekistane-dlya-razvitiya-e-kommerczii-vvodyatsya-novye-pravila-perechen/>

framework, the creation of a modern logistics infrastructure and the protection of the rights of market participants, which helps to strengthen trust in digital platforms and services.

These legislative initiatives create the basis for the safe and effective functioning of digital marketing in Uzbekistan, ensuring the protection of the rights of both consumers and businesses, and contributing to the further development of the country's digital economy.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

If we generalize from the results of research conducted by economists and define export potential, it is understood that the export potential of industrial enterprises is understood as the current or future gross production, personnel, financial capabilities, and the resistance of endogenous and exogenous factors to the impact of export potential in foreign economic trade. Based on the above definition of export potential, it is possible to draw up a scheme of factors affecting it.

Based on foreign experience, it should be noted that many economists have been engaged in the development of marketing principles and their application in practice. Among them, we can include such famous scientists as F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. Marshall.

While the research in the field of marketing conducted in our country for many years is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory in the economy. These include M. Mukhammedov, M. Pardaev, R. Ibragimov. YO. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhodjaev, B. Khodiev, D. Rakhimova, Sh. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musaeva and others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research process used a systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, and selective observation methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Digital marketing is a set of marketing strategies and tools aimed at promoting goods and services using Internet technologies. It is based on such key areas as:

- Search Engine Optimization (SEO)– increasing the visibility of web resources in search engines;
- Contextual advertising (PPC)– paid advertisements in search engines and on partner sites;
- Social Media Marketing (SMM)– promotion through social networks (Facebook, Instagram, Telegram, etc.);
- Content Marketing– creating useful and relevant content to engage your audience;
- Email Marketing– personalized interaction with clients through email newsletters;
- Analytics and big data– collection and analysis of data to optimize advertising campaigns.

Modern theories of digital marketing are based on the concept of Marketing 4.0 (F. Kotler), which combines traditional and digital methods of interaction with customers. An important aspect is personalization - the use of user data for targeted offering of goods and services.

Digital marketing in Uzbekistan is actively developing, which is due to the growth of the Internet audience, the development of e-commerce and the popularity of social networks. According to the report of the State Statistics Committee, in 2024 the number of Internet users in the country exceeded 27 million people, which opens up wide opportunities for online business promotion (table 1).

Table 1. Main digital marketing tools.

Tool	Description	Popular platforms in Uzbekistan
SEO (Search Engine Optimization)	Improving website positions in search engines	Google, Yandex, MyUZ, Top.uz
Contextual advertising (PPC)	Paid advertising in search engines and social networks	Google Ads, Yandex.Direct, Telegram Ads
SMM (social media marketing)	Promotion through social networks, content marketing	Telegram, Instagram, Facebook
Content Marketing	Creating useful and engaging content	Blogs, videos, infographics, podcasts
Influencer Marketing	Advertising through bloggers and opinion leaders	Instagram, TikTok, YouTube

Email Marketing	Personalized mailings and sales automation	Mailchimp, UniSender, SendPulse
Big Data and AI	Data analysis and customer behavior forecasting	AI chatbots, CRM systems

Local search engines and advertising platforms such as MyUz and Top.uz are actively developing in Uzbekistan. Google Ads and Yandex.Direct remain the main platforms for contextual advertising, and the popularity of Telegram Ads has also grown significantly.

Uzbekistan is one of the leaders in Central Asia in terms of social media user reach. According to the We Are Social (2024) report, the most popular platforms are:

Telegram (85% of Internet users);

Instagram (73%);

Facebook (41%).

This makes SMM one of the most effective tools for business promotion (table 2).

Table 2. Popularity of social networks in Uzbekistan (2024).

Social network	Number of users (million)	Share of Internet audience (%)
Telegram	23.0	85%
Instagram	19.8	73%
Facebook	11.1	41%
TikTok	10.4	38%
YouTube	8.2	30%

There is a growing demand for localized content in the country, including videos, infographics, and podcasts in the Uzbek language. Companies are investing in creating educational materials, blogs, and videos to attract customers.

Marketing through bloggers and opinion leaders has become widespread in Uzbekistan. Bloggers on Instagram and Telegram have the greatest influence, as well as video content on YouTube and TikTok.

Due to the development of online trading (Oson, Uzum Market, Apelsin), companies use CRM systems and AI analytics to automate marketing processes.

Examples of successful cases:

Uzum Market– a successful e-commerce platform that actively uses targeted advertising and SMM.

Korzinka.uz– a retail leader that has integrated a loyalty system and a mobile application.

Artel Electronics– a brand that promotes products through influencers and content marketing.

Despite the active development of the industry, there are barriers:

Limited access to international advertising platforms (due to currency and regulatory restrictions).

Low levels of digital literacy among small businesses.

High competition in online advertising and rising costs of promotion.

To overcome these problems, government support and advanced training of specialists in the field of digital marketing are important.

Thus, digital marketing in Uzbekistan is a promising direction that allows businesses to effectively attract customers and develop in the context of digital transformation.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In recent years, digital marketing in Uzbekistan has demonstrated rapid development, driven by the growth of the Internet audience, the popularity of social networks and the active implementation of digital technologies in business. Companies are adapting their marketing strategies using SEO, contextual advertising, SMM, content marketing and AI tools to personalize interactions with customers. Government support and adopted regulations contribute to the development of e-commerce and digital entrepreneurship, creating favorable conditions for business growth in the online environment.

However, despite the positive trends, the industry still faces certain challenges, such as high competition, the need to improve the digital literacy of entrepreneurs, and limited access to international advertising platforms. For the further development of digital marketing in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to:

- Development of educational programs – creation of courses and trainings for entrepreneurs and marketers on modern digital strategies.

- Government support for digital business – tax breaks and grants for startups working in the field of digital marketing and e-commerce.

- Content localization – active development of Uzbek-language content to increase audience engagement.

- Investments in technological solutions – development of AI analytics, automated CRM systems and big data tools.

- Expanding advertising opportunities – improving access to international advertising platforms and developing local advertising services.

Thus, digital marketing in Uzbekistan has significant potential, and with the effective use of modern tools and strategies, its impact on the country's economy will only increase.

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